

Meeting the future metro network challenges and requirements by adopting programmable S-BVT with direct-detection and PDM functionality

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an advanced programmable sliceable-bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) with polarization division multiplexing (PDM) capability as a key enabler to fulfill the requirements for future 5G networks. Thanks to its cost-effective optoelectronic front-end based on orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) technology and direct-detection (DD), the proposed S-BVT becomes suitable for next generation highly flexible and scalable metro networks. Polarization beam splitters (PBSs) and controllers (PCs), available on-demand, are included at the transceivers and at the network nodes, further enhancing the system flexibility and promoting an efficient use of the spectrum. 40G-100G PDM transmission has been experimentally demonstrated, within a 4-node photonic mesh network (ADRENALINE testbed), implementing a simplified equalization process.

Keywords: Adaptive bit/power loading (BL/PL), sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT), polarization division multiplexing (PDM), direct-detection (DD), orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), optical metro networks.

1. Introduction

The increasing number of new emerging services, expanding number of connected devices and huge increase of data volumes/traffic promote the evolution of current optical metro networks towards more efficient and flexible/programmable solutions. The emerging 5G optical networks will be built to include modular network functions and capabilities that could be deployed and scaled on demand. These flexible functions can be included in the cloud, imposing challenging performance targets/bandwidth requirements in order to cope with the varied and heterogeneous range of future services [1]. Hence, some identified key network/system requirements must be considered for a suitable network design [1, 2]: (i) network complexity reduction, (ii) flexibility and capacity increase, (iii) programmability extension, (iv) network resources abstraction and (v) new functionalities development.

In order to deal with (i) requisite, transceivers play an important role. Thus, optical implementations based on simple transmitter/receiver cost-effective architectures with direct-detection (DD) have gained special attention. Thanks to the use of single side band (SSB) transmission, resilience to fiber impairments increases enhancing system performance [3].

So far, one of the viable approaches to increase system flexibility and enable programmability, identified as (ii) and (iii) requirements, is the adoption of sliceable bandwidth variable transceivers (S-BVT). In fact, they aggregate different slices/signals at variable data rates in a single high capacity optical flow [4, 5, 6]. This flow can be disaggregated at an intermediate network node in order to reach multiple destinations. Additionally, thanks to the implementation of advanced modulation formats, such as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), finer granularity is achieved. Thus, allowing to change/optimize the number of bits per symbol at the subcarrier level. This optimization can be performed by the implementation of bit/power loading (BL/PL) algorithms, according to the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of each subcarrier [7, 8]. Hence, the impact of transmission impairments (e.g. chromatic dispersion, CD) and

hardware limitations (e.g. digital-to-analog converter, DAC, bandwidth) on the system performance can be reduced [7].

On the other hand, network resources can be abstracted. Specifically, modular network functions can be implemented, at the control plane level, in order to efficiently enable/disable the polarization dimension, meeting the (iv) requisite. For instance, two OFDM signals can be multiplexed into orthogonal polarization states (polarization division multiplexing, PDM), enabling 50 % spectral saving and promoting resource dynamicity [9, 10, 11].

However, at the increase of the optical link length, polarization mode dispersion (PMD) effect appears causing the misalignment of the state of polarization (SOP) between the OFDM subcarriers and the optical carrier and resulting in power fading [12, 13, 14].

Different solutions, applied either in the electrical or optical domain, have been proposed in the literature to mitigate the PMD impairment trading off performance versus complexity. Specifically, electrical solutions can rely on linear and nonlinear equalization, which can be based on multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) processing, implemented with a polarization diversity receiver [3, 10, 11, 15]. Additionally, polarization tracking algorithms can be also implemented in the digital domain to control the SOP of the received signal [16]. Conversely, optical solutions consist of adapting the signal polarization at the receiver side by means of polarization controllers (PCs), which can be designed to be fully programmable and automatic [17, 18, 19]. As an example, in [17], an automatic polarization control system was designed, which adjusts the SOP of one of the PDM signals to the X-axes in order to be linearly polarized, presenting minimum radio frequency (RF) power. Hence, in order to properly detect both polarization components, the automatic PC is controlled with a RF power monitor to minimize the RF power.

Finally, according to requisite (v) new functionalities must be developed in order to fulfill the design principles for 5G networks. The proposed new functionalities include PDM slice-ability and forward error correction (FEC) adaptability, which can be reconfigured by a software-defined networking (SDN)

controller through SDN agents [20, 4]. Specifically, the SDN controller interacts with, for example, an active stateful PCE for the channel/path computation, delegating the lightpath provisioning to an underlying, e.g. based general multiprotocol label switching (GMPLS) control plane [21, 22]. In our previous publication [20], we proposed a novel flexible and cost-effective S-BVT with DD including these advanced functionalities suitable for inter-data center (DC) communication.

In this paper, we propose the implementation of programmable S-BVT with polarization multiplexing capability as a solution to satisfy the stringent requirements identified to deploy future 5G network. Additionally, in section 2, the system model of the proposed S-BVT with advanced functionalities is described. In section 3, a numerical analysis in the presence of PMD impairment is performed. Variable bit/power loading per subcarrier and adaptive data assignment per polarization is enabled to efficiently adapt the system to the channel profile. In section 4, polarization slice-ability at both the transceiver and the network nodes is further investigated considering the experimental set-up within the ADRENALINE testbed, performed in [20]. Different polarization components (horizontal -H- and vertical -V), each corresponding to a single slice, can be enabled/disabled and transmitted along different optical paths, which are dynamically provisioned by the SDN controller promoting flexible spectrum usage. Moreover, two optical paths of the ADRENALINE testbed have been characterized in terms of PMD in order to model them in simulations and compare the results with the experiments. Specifically, simulation analysis including different equalization processes (e.g. independent and MIMO equalizers) has been performed. Finally, in section 5, the conclusions are drawn.

2. System model: Enabling PDM capability at the S-BVTx and S-BVRx

In this section, an S-BVT with PDM capability is presented as a key enabler for achieving high data rate transmission and enhancing network flexi-

Figure 1: Building blocks of the proposed sliceable BVT with PDM capability.

bility/programmability, (ii) and (iii) network requirements identified in Sec. 1. The building blocks of the sliceable transceiver, bandwidth variable transmitter (BVTx) and bandwidth variable receiver (BVRx), are based on OFDM technology (see Fig. 1). At the digital signal processing (DSP) blocks of the S-
95 BVTx, randomly generated bit streams are parallelized and mapped into BPSK and optimized m -QAM constellations ($m = 2^l$; $2 \leq l \leq 8$), according to the BL/PL algorithm for adaptive mapping [7]. In particular, the SNR per sub-carrier is estimated to activate the BL/PL algorithm at the transmitter side; the network experience/information about the channel is improved [7]. Then,
100 training symbols (TS) are added to properly equalize data at the receiver side. A cyclic prefix (CP) is included after performing the inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT). Data are serialized, clipped and upconverted to a radio frequency of half the signal bandwidth in order to transmit real symbols. Hence, no guard band is left between the optical carrier and the OFDM signal. Clipping
105 is performed in order to mitigate the peak-to-average power ratio impairment, which appears in OFDM systems introducing distortion [23]. A pre-emphasis digital filter is then used to compensate the limited bandwidth of each DAC. After this stage, multiple optical flows are generated at different data rates, by means of tuneable laser sources (TLSs) and external Mach-Zehnder modulators
110 (MZMs). The center wavelength and power of the TLS as well as the MZM

bias point can be suitably programmed by the SDN controller through SDN agents, according to [4]. The SDN controller can also dynamically assign these flows into orthogonal polarization components/states according to the channel condition and network requirements by enabling the corresponding polarization beam combiner (PBC). Finally, the multiple flows are aggregated with a spectrum selective switch (SSS), which acts as both aggregator and SSB filter bank. Specifically, the bandwidth, attenuation and center wavelength of each filter port can also be reconfigured according to the target requirements [4]. Then, the aggregated flow is transmitted over the network.

At the receiver side, the SSS distributes the flows towards the different BVRx, corresponding to the S-BVRx building blocks. Then, each polarization beam splitter (PBS) can be enabled to properly separate the orthogonal polarization components. For a practical and low cost implementation, the PC, the PBS and eventually the photodetection stage of each S-BVTx/S-BVRx building block, can be integrated in silicon-on-insulator substrate enabling to change the polarization arbitrarily [24, 25, 26]. A DD cost-effective front-end, including a pre-amplification stage an array of PIN photodiodes, is considered in order to tackle (i) requirement. Finally, the photodetected signals are analog-to-digital converted, with an array of ADCs, for post-processing at the DSP receiver blocks. Specifically, before removing the CP and implementing the FFT, the received signals are downconverted to baseband and parallelized. Then, equalization process, which can be based on minimum mean square error (MMSE) is performed, enabling a flexible selection of the modulation format, according to [8]. In particular, circular 8QAM format is implemented achieving an enhanced system performance [8]. In order to fully compensate PMD impairment, MIMO equalization can be adopted increasing DSP complexity and reducing system flexibility, due to the need of a co-processing reception. However, as the PMD is not a major issue when transmitting over optical links of few hundred kilometers targeted in metro network, alternative/simpler equalizations can be considered. For example, independent equalization based on either Zero Forcing (ZF) or MMSE can be implemented together with the adoption of PCs, which

can be automatically controlled [17], to align the SOP at the receiver and limit the influence of PMD. As a result, the receiver DSP complexity is reduced and a distributed reception can be enabled increasing the system/network flexibility.
145 Finally, TS removal, demapping and serialization processes are performed.

3. Numerical analysis of PDM effect on system performance

PDM-enabled S-BVT has been presented, in Sec. 2, as a promising solution to fulfill some of the network requisites described in Sec. 1. One of the major issues that presents PDM transmission is the appearance of PMD impairment.
150 Hence, in this section PMD is investigated for different optical links up to one span of 80 km, considering the proposed S-BVT of Fig. 1. For the simulations, two orthogonally polarized 20 GHz SSB OFDM signals are created with a 512 points IFFT/FFT. A total number of 100 OFDM frames are sent considering a hard-decision (HD)-FEC, at $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ BER threshold. The overheads due
155 to TS, CP and FEC are 8%, 1.9% and 7%, respectively. In particular, MIMO linear equalizer based on ZF has been implemented by setting half of the TS to 0, in order to create orthogonal symbols [11]. Hence, increased overhead is needed in comparison with independent equalization. The Levin Campello rate adaptive BL/PL algorithm is applied for maximizing the capacity of each
160 slice, corresponding to a polarization component, at the target performance [7]. MZMs, working at the quadrature point, are driven by a single TLS centered at 1550.12 nm and with +13 dBm output power. A no-guard-interval SSB scheme is considered for further increasing spectral saving and resilience against CD [27]. The propagation over an standard single mode fiber (SSMF) is modeled
165 with the split-step Fourier method. Specifically, a fiber dispersion coefficient of 16.5 ps/nm/km, nonlinear coefficient of $1.2 W^{-1} km^{-1}$, 0.29 dB/km attenuation, 10^{-7} birefringence, 100 m correlation distance and variable PMD coefficient are considered. The preamplifiers have been modeled at constant gain with 4.7 dB noise figure.

170 The robustness, in terms of achieved net data rate, of the proposed sys-

Figure 2: Achieved total net data rate for different PMD coefficients.

tem with MIMO equalization against PMD impairment, can be seen in Fig. 2. There, the aggregated data rate of the two transmitted polarization components is depicted also considering different fiber links of SSMF. Specifically, data rate penalties higher than 10 Gb/s are observed at $1 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{(km)}$, compared to the ideal case (0 PMD) for the different analyzed links. Actually, SSMF links deployed in metro networks present a maximum PMD coefficient of $0.2 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{(km)}$ [28]. From the figure, it can be observed that for such low PMD coefficients (e.g. $0.02 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{(km)}$ and $0.05 \text{ ps}/\sqrt{(km)}$) the achieved total data rate decreases in few Gb/s. Hence, simpler alternative equalization schemes, such as independent equalization based on MMSE, arise as suitable solutions to provide a more flexible transmission over metro networks (related to (ii) requirement).

4. Functionalities evaluation for the fulfillment of network requisites

Once we have evaluated the impact of the PMD on the system performance and evidenced the possibility of including independent equalization at the receiver to further increase resource dynamicity, we discuss and investigate how to fulfill the network requisites, previously identified in section 1. For this purpose,

Figure 3: Experimental setup. Digital to analog converter (DAC); optical amplifier (OA); Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM); spectrum selective switch (SSS), tuneable laser source (TLS); polarization controller (PC); polarization beam splitter/combiner (PBS/PBC); variable optical attenuator (VOA); optical spectrum analyzer (OSA); transimpedance amplifier (TIA); oscilloscope (OSC).

we propose the experimental set-up of Fig. 3, where the S-BVTx/S-BVRx building blocks were already reported in [20]. Here, we give additional details and insides and provide a comparison between experimental and numerical results.

190 Two fully flexible OFDM BVTs are enabled in order to transmit two polarization components, using a 64 GSa/s DAC for generating two 20 GHz slices. However, multiple OFDM BVTs can be enabled and allocated in different wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) channels in order to create an aggregated high capacity flow, according to the network requirement/targets [4]. By adopt-

195 ing the scheme of Fig. 3, the number of TLS and the total bandwidth occupancy are halved. Hence, for generating two slices a single TLS at 1550.12 nm with +13 dBm output power is required. In fact, modular functions could be implemented, at the control plane level, in order to enable/disable the polarization functionality according to the network targets, dealing with (iv) requirement

200 regarding resource abstraction. After modulation, a PBC is used to create two orthogonally polarized components (H&V). A delay of 3 times the TS duration is included in one of the branches to properly decorrelate the two slices. The SSS bandwidth is 25 GHz and the optical amplifier (OA) output power, at the transmitter, is set to +1 dBm. A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is used for

205 optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) measurements, performed within 0.1 nm. Both slices are photodetected with a 20 GHz PIN and converted to digital by means of an oscilloscope (OSC) running at 100 GSa/s. Similarly, a single slice can be transmitted, if one of the BVT transceivers is not enabled. With the adoption of the proposed S-BVT, new advanced functionalities such as polar-
210 ization slice-ability and FEC adaptability can be exploited in the network, also meeting (v) requisite.

A B2B configuration and different paths of the ADRENALINE network have been considered in order to demonstrate the proposed new functionalities and the fulfilment of the identified network requirements. The ADRENALINE net-
215 work consists of 4 optical nodes interconnected with different SSMF links [21]. Firstly, variable FEC selection is enabled at the proposed S-BVT, evaluating the contribution per slice in B2B configuration. Accordingly, an optimized spectral usage and variable data rate per slice can be achieved targeting the selected FEC/performance, dealing with (ii) and (v) requisites. PDM functionality is
220 further investigated considering different paths of the ADRENALINE network, and an additional 10 km fiber spool, at both transceiver and network level, fulfilling all the identified requirements. In particular, different paths of the ADRENALINE network are characterized in terms of PMD, in order to implement reliable simulation models. Furthermore, we investigate the penalty in
225 terms of data rate of enabling/disabling the polarization functionality for an efficient control/management of the network resources. Polarization slice-ability can also be enabled at the network node by considering PBS and PC, available on-demand [29], to enhance the flexibility and promote a dynamic service provisioning targeted in future 5G networks. As demonstrated in [4], the SDN
230 controller can establish an optical path, as well as program/reconfigure the S-BVT, according to the channel condition. Thus, two polarization components can be separated at an intermediate network node and transmitted towards different destinations. Similarly, if multiple slices are enabled creating an aggregated high capacity flow, this can be further sliced into data flows with less
235 capacity, concurrently serving multiple destination nodes at variable rate [4].

Figure 4: BER vs OSNR of H component for different target FEC/rate.

4.1. Enabling FEC functionality

Different FEC/BER thresholds can be used at each BVT, achieving variable data rates per slice and adapting the energy consumption accordingly [30]. Specifically, the most appropriate FEC threshold can be reconfigured regarding the established optical path, at both BVTx and BVRx, by the SDN controller

240 the established optical path, at both BVTx and BVRx, by the SDN controller to maximize the energy efficiency and enable a target data rate [30]. Alternative HD-FEC or soft-decision (SD)-FEC, corresponding to an overhead of 7% ($4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ BER threshold) and 20% ($2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ BER threshold) has been respectively considered in the experiments [31]. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the system

245 performance in terms of BER at the varying of the OSNR for the different polarization components (H&V) in a B2B configuration. HD-FEC is ensured transmitting a maximum net data rate of 52.9 Gb/s and 48.5 Gb/s in H and V component, respectively (101.4 Gb/s total data rate). The performance difference between polarization components is due to the fact that two MZMs of

250 different manufacturers have been used in the set-up. Considering SD-FEC, lower OSNR values are required to ensure the same data rates at the expense of higher computational complexity. Hence, for the remainder of the paper,

Figure 5: BER vs OSNR of V component for different target FEC/rate.

Figure 6: Polarization slice-ability assessment

HD-FEC with a target BER of $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ is considered in order to relax the required/needed overhead and pose more stringent performance requirements.

255 4.2. Polarization slice-ability

An additional functionality, that has been presented in [20], is the polarization slice-ability enabled by the adoption of (automatic) PCs and by the implementation of independent equalization at the receiver side. Here, addi-

Table 1: ADRENALINE optical paths characterization: PMD analysis

Parameters	Length:35 km	Length:50 km
PMD Value	0.319 ps	0.356 ps
PMD Coeff.	0.0539 ps/\sqrt{km}	0.0504 ps/\sqrt{km}
Gauss. Compliance Fact.	0.822	0.826
Accum. 2nd Order PMD	0.0460 $ps/nm(0.0586 ps^2)$	0.0573 $ps/nm(0.0733 ps^2)$
Second PMD Coeff.	0.0013 $ps/nm.km(0.0017 ps^2.km)$	0.0011 $ps/nm.km(0.0015 ps^2.km)$

tional numerical and experimental analysis considering different optical links of the ADRENALINE testbed, featuring distances up to 60 km, is provided in order to investigate the robustness of the proposed S-BVT against PMD. Firstly, we have experimentally measured the PMD coefficient of the 35 km and 50 km optical testbed links in order to characterize them in simulations. A PMD analyzer source working in the C+L band has been placed at OXC-2 and a PMD analyzer at ROADM-1 and ROADM-2 to measure the PMD parameters of the corresponding paths (see Fig. 3). The achieved results are summarized in Table 1, where it can be seen that PMD coefficients of about $0.05 ps/\sqrt{km}$ have been measured for both network links: 35 km and 50 km. Additionally, the variation of the signal intensity in %, versus the instantaneous delay between polarization components, dispersion group delay (DGD), is depicted in Fig. 7 (a) and (b) for the 35 km and 50 km path, respectively. The measured intensity is directly related to the normalized Stokes parameter S_0 . The PMD value is given by the average of the DGD probability distribution and it is used to calculate the PMD coefficient, which represents the characteristics of one particular length of fiber. Taking into account the measured low PMD coefficients and the results of Fig. 2, independent equalization implementation at the Rx side is further motivated and presented as suitable solution for the proposed transceivers, enabling flexible metro networks/systems.

After link characterization, the 35 km path (OXC-2→ROADM-1) is assessed, analyzing the achieved data rate per slice (see Fig. 6). In this particular case, 44 Gb/s and 38 Gb/s can be transmitted in H and V polarization components, at 33.5 dB OSNR, ensuring $4.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ BER, as reported in Fig. 8. Additionally, a maximum penalty of 10 Gb/s is observed between polarization components

Figure 7: PMD characterization: Intensity in % vs DGD for the (a) 35 km and (b) 50 km ADRENALINE paths.

Figure 8: Achieved data rate per polarization component vs OSNR after 35 km link; (inset) captured spectra at OSC of H (black) and V (gray) components after 35 km path.

due to set-up implementation. In particular, the two different MZMs used in the
 285 set-up shows different performance, as also observed in the inset of Fig. 8, where
 the received spectra, at the OSC, are depicted. This performance degradation
 between polarization components was also evidenced in [20] for a B2B configura-
 tion. However, the use of photonic technologies and photonic integration can

be envisioned in order to meet the network requirements in terms of cost, power
290 consumption and footprint, also expecting enhanced system performance.

As a next step, the two slices have been transmitted in orthogonal polar-
ization states over the 50 km and 60 km paths considering in simulation, both
MIMO and independent equalization stages (MMSE for comparison with ex-
periments). From Fig 9, it can be seen that independent equalization works
295 properly up to 60 km optical path, where the data rate decreases in more than
10 Gb/s when comparing to MIMO scheme. This is due to the fact, that the
analyzed links present low PMD coefficients, according to the previous exper-
imental results (see Table 1). From the figure, it can also be observed that
MIMO equalizer outperforms MMSE independent equalizer when the assessed
300 network path is longer than 50 km. In this case, a more robust equalization,
such as MIMO, is required due to PMD issues at the expense of increased over-
head, receiver complexity and reduced system flexibility. For the analyzed metro
network paths (shorter than 60 km) MMSE independent equalizer becomes a
suitable solution, as distributed receivers can be implemented enhancing system
305 simplicity and flexibility without performance degradation (see Fig. 9). In fact,
slightly higher data rate is achieved when compared to ZF-based MIMO equal-
izer in B2B and after 35 km path. This is due to the fact that MMSE offers the
possibility to implement a wider variety of constellations, such as circular-8QAM
format, as investigated in [8]. Additionally, experiments have been compared
310 with performance simulations showing good agreement between numerical and
experimental results, according to the figure. The BER per polarization compo-
nent of all the analyzed numerical and experimental cases, including MIMO and
independent equalization are depicted in Fig. 10. It can be observed that the
obtained BER results are below the target HD-FEC threshold after transmission
315 over different network paths.

Finally, the data rate penalty due to PMD, of H polarization component,
has been experimentally evaluated for the 35 km and 50 km optical paths, as
depicted in Fig. 11. By enabling polarization slice-ability and implementing
independent equalization, a 50% spectral saving is achieved at the expense of

Figure 9: Total net data rate at the varying of the optical path.

Figure 10: BER vs distance using independent and MIMO equalization.

320 < 10% data rates decrease, when transmitting over the analyzed network paths. Hence, it is demonstrated that the proposed PDM-enabler S-BVT meets the previously identified requirements arising as a suitable solution for future 5G metro networks.

Figure 11: Data rate penalty due to PMD

4.3. Enabling polarization functionality at the network nodes

325 Polarization slice-ability is also proposed at the network edge/intermediate nodes in order to support/include new programmability features fitting all the identified requirements, (i)-(v), of the target metro networks. A new degree of flexibility is included at the network level by exploiting the polarization dimension. Specifically, the proposed set-up and node architecture, depicted in
 330 Fig. 3, includes a polarization enabler block, available on-demand, which allows

Figure 12: PDM-enabled network nodes: Scenarios

Figure 13: Achieved net data rate per polarization component. Scenarios a-f depicted in Fig. 12

the SDN controller to dynamically distribute orthogonal polarizations over different network optical links. The proposed block consists of a PBS and a PC, which can also be automatic in order to be adopted in a realistic scenario [17], allowing the SDN agents to suitably program and re-configure the transmitted polarization components. Hence, network flexibility is further enhanced and distributed reception and higher spectral efficiency is achieved.

Fig. 12 summarizes the scenarios analyzed to demonstrate this network functionality achieving variable rate/reach per slice, as shown in Fig. 13. Specifically, Fig. 13, reports a set of results obtained in [20], to provide further discussion in line with the fulfilment of the network requisites. In Fig. 12 (a), H and V polarization components are separated at OXC-2 and then independently transmitted towards ROADM-1 and ROADM-2 through a 35 km and 50 km path, respectively. From the results, summarized in Fig. 13, it can be observed that H and V components are successfully transmitted, at the target BER, achieving

Figure 14: Experimental SNR estimation per subcarrier

345 38.6 Gb/s and 35.9 Gb/s net data rates, respectively. In contrast, in Fig. 12 (b) both slices are jointly transmitted into orthogonal polarizations along 10 km path towards an intermediate network node. Thanks to the polarization slice-ability of the node, the two polarization components reach different destinations after splitting the two contributions and promoting a flexible and an efficient use of the network resources, (ii) requisite. In this case, the data rate decreases of about 1 Gb/s, compared to Fig. 12 (a) scenario. Thus, PMD is not a major issue after 10 km path. In fact, thanks to the use of PCs, we are able to align the SOP, compensating the introduced rotation/retardation.

355 Finally, PDM slice-ability is further analyzed considering also longer optical network paths, corresponding to Fig. 12 (c)-(f). For these cases, both PDM slices reach an intermediate network node after 1-hop path of either 35 km or 50 km. Then, they are separated and distributed towards different receivers, considering a total transmission path of up to 185 km. Specifically, in Fig. 12 (c) and (d), both polarization components are transmitted within the same optical

Figure 15: Bit assignment per subcarrier of (a) H component and (b) V component.

channel/bandwidth along the 35 km path. In both cases, they are separated
in an intermediate network node, where H component is demultiplexed and
V is send towards 10 km and 50 km path, respectively. In Fig. 12 (e), V is
transmitted at 14.4 Gb/s net data rate up to 185 km (2-hop), while H is retrieved
after the first 35 km (Fig. 13). From Fig. 13, it can also be observed that V
polarization component achieves 20.3 Gb/s net data rate after 60 km path,
sharing spectral resources, with H polarization, along 50 km, corresponding
to Fig. 12 (f). The two polarization contributions are successfully separated
and redistributed over the network, supporting polarization slice-ability. In this
particular case, the SNR estimation of both polarization components, as well as
the bit assignment per subcarrier are depicted in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 (a) and (b),
respectively. From the figures it can be seen that one polarization component
is more affected by fiber impairments, as travels for a longer path, and hence
lower bits per symbol are assigned to the subcarriers. As an additional remark,
filtering effects due to passing through cascaded network nodes can be limited
by the implementation of bit/power loading algorithms, according to [32].

The proposed node architecture enables an efficient management of the
available resources, enhancing system/network flexibility and increasing data
rate/spectral efficiency, as key requirements for future elastic optical networks.
In particular, network resources and PDM functionality can be abstracted to
reduce network complexity, and increase flexibility, dealing with (iv) requisite.
Hence, PDM functionality can be enabled/disabled by the control plane, at both

the S-BVT and network node level, according to the requirements and targets (data rate/spectral efficiency).

5. Conclusion

385 In this work, different network requirements have been identified and tackled in order to promote the evolution of current metro optical networks towards future flexible 5G solutions. By the adoption of programmable OFDM-based S-BVTs with cost-effective DD reception, high data rate transmission as well as network complexity/cost reduction, resource abstraction and programmabil-
390 ity/flexibility enhancement are achieved. New advanced functionalities have also been further investigated, at both the transceiver and network nodes, consisting of polarization exploitation and adaptive FEC selection. Specifically, the SDN controller would be able to reconfigure the transceiver by suitably enabling/disabling PDM slice-ability at each S-BVTx/S-BVRx building block
395 according to the network condition. 40G-100G PDM transmission has been numerically and experimentally demonstrated within the ADRENALINE network ensuring HD-FEC. Hence, the proposed system arises as a promising solution to fully exploit, in an affordable and sustainable manner, flexibility and programmability in the network, meeting the essential requisites necessary to
400 support heterogenous advanced 5G services.

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